

Seasonality of tourist points of interest – a big data approach

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Highlights

- We used big data from passive location events recorded by smartphones via the wetter.com-application to determine levels of seasonality for 11 PoI in the years 2022 and 2023.
- We use three seasonality indicators to assess the level of seasonality: Relative TCSI, corrected Gini and the share of the top 3 weeks in a year.
- Results show significant differences between PoI and between years, but a high correlation between indicators.
- Results can be used as reference points for other research on PoI seasonality.

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Introduction

Recently, there was a call to use big data tracking techniques for analysing tourist mobility patterns in different seasons and location (Chen et al., 2024). However, using Big Data sources with high spatial and – in our case here much more important – high temporal resolution is well suited for analysing seasonality in tourism. Ahas et al. (2017) for example use passive mobile positioning data to analyse the seasonality of foreign visitors in Estland.

Although many analyses of seasonality have already been carried out in the past, these are essentially limited to higher aggregated levels such as countries, federal states, districts or regions. We go one step further by analysing the seasonality of different attraction points in Germany with the help of mobile location events from a weather application (see for Germany e.g. Eisenstein & Reif, 2021). Therefore, the aim of this paper is to analyse the seasonality of heterogeneous tourist attractions. Using various indicators for tourism seasonality in 12 different classes of points of interest in Germany, a conceptual basis for general seasonal patterns of these attraction points is created.

Seasonality in tourism

In time series analysis, seasonality simply refers to a recurring (periodic) pattern in the data, mostly within a year (De Livera et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2022). “The word *seasonality* itself highlights the strong relationship between systematic intra-year variations and astronomical seasons.” (Lo Magno et al., 2017, p. 55).

In tourism contexts, “seasonality” is frequently used as another word for “concentration”: “Seasonality’ refers to the tendency of tourist flows to

be concentrated into relatively short periods of the year.” (Witt et al., 2014, p. 41). This goes along with a mostly negative connotation of seasonality, which is “... generally recognized as a perennial problem and negative attribute of tourism” (Yabanci, 2023, p. 273). Although fluctuating demand throughout the year is the cause, from an economic point of view a *problem* arises when available capacities (e.g. hotel beds, bicycles, etc.) are not utilised. For these economic reasons, it is easy to understand why seasonality is considered one of the main problems, especially for mature destinations (Duro, 2018, p. 615).

“One might, with some legitimacy, ask if indeed it is appropriate to continue to try to ‘solve’ this ‘problem’ given its apparent intractability” (Butler, 2001, p. 5).

Seasonality can be understood as an interplay between demand-related attributes (When are the school holidays?), supply-related attributes in the destination (Does it rain a lot there in winter?) and intervening destination management variables in the destinations (Do we lower prices in the rainy season?) (Figure 1). Butler (2001, p. 7 ff.) therefore identifies five reasons for seasonality:

1. Natural variations (weather, seasons)
2. Human actions and policies (e.g. school holidays)
3. Social seasonality (social pressure and fashion)
4. Climatic seasonality (sporting season)
5. Inertia and tradition

Figure 1: Influences on Patterns of Tourism Seasonality in Destinations

Source: Authors, after Butler, 2001, p. 9

Spatial Aspects and Patterns of Seasonality

Even if seasonality is essentially a temporal phenomenon, seasonality in tourism always has a spatial perspective. The location of destinations and attraction points is therefore an important factor to consider. Due to the multi-optionality of the offer and the high demand for business trips, which frequently have a balancing effect on seasonality, urban destinations for example have a lower seasonality than rural destinations. Peripheral destinations are also generally more difficult to reach, which is reflected in a higher seasonality, similar to climatic conditions in the destinations, which essentially result from the distance to the equator (Butler, 2001, p. 14f).

Seasonality indicators

From the literature (Butler & Mao, 1997; Koenig-Lewis & Bischoff, 2005; Rau, 2007) we can identify four main groups of seasonality indicators (Figure 2). A first group, which is the main focus of this paper, is measuring the *level* or *extent* of seasonality, while the second group tries to identify *patterns* of seasonality. The third group measures extent and pattern based upon time-series decomposition, and the fourth group is covering statistical tests.

Figure 2: Groups of seasonality indicators

Source: Authors

In addition, a fifth group, qualitative coding, could be mentioned: In these studies (Agius & Briguglio, 2021; Chiriko, 2021; Su et al., 2022), seasonality is used as a factor in qualitative interviews and identified through coding methods. However, this method is outside the realm of (quantitative) indicators.

Level of seasonality

Level of seasonality can be measured by indicators in six groups (Figure 3).

The first group of indicators can be described as a **peak indicator** approach. In this group, indicators are based upon the relationship between some “top” values and the rest of the distribution. Examples are the top share approach, seasonal range, *seasonality indicator* proposed by Lundtorp (2001), Yacoumi’s (1980) *seasonality ratio* or the *Winter/Summer ratio*.

Figure 3: Measurement methods for levels of seasonality

Source: Authors

A second group of indicators considers the **dispersion of demand** over time by using the derivations from the mean. Examples are the *average absolute deviation*, *variance*, *standard deviation* and the *variation coefficient*.

A third group of indicators uses **measures of inequality**. From the large number of measures, the literature mostly uses the Gini, Theil or Hoover index. As tourism seasonality is usually seen as a phenomenon of **concentration**, the Herfindahl-Hirschmann concentration index (HHI) can be used to measure seasonality.

A fifth group uses a **cyclical approach** to identify pattern and amplitude of seasonality. The (Relative) Transportation Cost Seasonality Index TCSI or RTCSI (Lo Magno et al., 2017) considers the cyclical nature of

seasonality so that in an annual context the months January and November are closer than January and August. This is particularly useful in bimodal demand curves, e.g. with high demand in winter *and* in summer. A standalone software for Microsoft Windows and an R package (*spatialct*) are available to calculate TCSI and RTCSI (Lo Magno, 2017; Lo Magno et al., 2020).

Lastly, there are **composite indicators** which try to integrate various data sets on the same object (Lozano et al., 2021; Martín Martín et al., 2019).

Patterns of seasonality

The identification of seasonality patterns has a long tradition in tourism research. It goes back to Butler and Mao (1997), who identified three basic patterns of seasonality (one peak, two peaks, no peak) for monthly demand data in large-scale destinations (countries, regions, cities). In addition, shoulder seasons can easily be identified. Shoulder seasons are time units between high and low demand seasons where demand is close to the average. Other patterns exist: for China, a multimodal pattern was identified with peaks in March/April, July/August, October and December (Zhang et al., 2022, p. 2).

There are three main routes towards the identification of seasonality patterns: Visual inspection, lag analysis and machine learning.

Time Series Decomposition

Another approach is that of **time series decomposition**. This approach tries to identify the seasonal component in any time series through statistical decomposition (Duro, 2018; Hylleberg, 2023; Rosselló & Sansó, 2017). A standard time series model has four components, trend (T), season (S), cycle (C) and irregular (I) fluctuations, and it might be either additive or multiplicative (Ogasawara, 2022):

$$y = f(T, S, C, I)$$

The idea of decomposition is to identify the value of each of these components. Isolating the seasonal component can then be used to assess the extent of seasonality. Software packages like *feasts* for R (O'Hara-Wild et al., 2024) automatically extract the seasonal component from a time series

Statistical Tests for Seasonality

While all of the methods mentioned so far fall into the category of descriptive statistics, tests are part of inferential statistics. Examples are the χ^2 -Goodness-of-Fit Test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, Edwards' Test, and, as an example for a non-parametric test, Hewitt's Test (Rau, 2007, p. 44 ff.). Obviously, it is possible to measure tourism seasonality from samples, as is done in surveys. Then, it can be useful to employ statistical tests for seasonality. The typical case, however, seems to be to assess tourism demand seasonality from official statistics or counts. Then, the data cover the whole population and the application of statistical tests is not useful.

Choice of indicators

For this paper we use mainly the RTCSI because it better reflects real-world problems coming out of seasonality. These problems tend to be less severe in a bi- or multimodal distribution compared to a unimodal distribution. RTCSI reflects bi- or multimodality better than other measures. However, we additionally report the Gini index because it frequently used in the literature and the top-z-share value because it is for practical relevance.

Data Source

We use data from passive location events from smartphones from the provider wetter.com. A detailed description of the data and spatial polygons can be found in Engelhardt et al. (2024). Data is available on the basis of calendar weeks for the years 2022 and 2023 (visitors and visits). The following use cases in Germany were selected in order to analyse the most heterogeneous points of interest possible with regard to the seasonality of demand.

- Zoo: Hagenbecks Tierpark, Hamburg
- Pool: Dünetherme, St. Peter-Ording
- Edutainment Centre: Multimar Wattforum, Tönning
- City Centre: Jungfernstieg, Hamburg
- Museum: German Museum, Munich
- Shopping Centre: Wertheim Village, Wertheim
- Beach: Beach Scharbeutz
- Lake: Biggensee, Olpe district
- Cultural Landmark: Neuschwanstein Castle
- National Park: Bavarian Forest, Bavaria
- Camping ground: Naturcamping Prinzenholz, Eutin
- Ski area: Willingen

Results

We first plotted the visitors for all points of interest over the two years for visual analysis of seasonality patterns and peak identification (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Visitors by week in each PoI, years 2022 and 2023

The visual analysis shows a heterogeneous distribution of visitors at the locations with different seasonal patterns. For example, we can identify at the beach in Scharbeutz a clear peak in the summer, while we tend to see a more balanced visitor flow in the factory outlet centre of Wertheim Village.

Table 1: Selected seasonality indicators

PoI Year	Top 3 share	Gini (Corrected)	Relative TCSI
Bayerischer Wald_2022	0.080	0.109	0.068
Bayerischer Wald_2023	0.082	0.125	0.086
Deutsches Museum_2022	0.112	0.269	0.172
Deutsches Museum_2023	0.094	0.128	0.032
Dünentherme SPO_2022	0.103	0.226	0.094
Dünentherme SPO_2023	0.121	0.329	0.262
Hagenbecks Tierpark_2022	0.117	0.278	0.206
Hagenbecks Tierpark_2023	0.140	0.298	0.236
Jungfernstieg_2022	0.109	0.184	0.057
Jungfernstieg_2023	0.119	0.205	0.099
Multimar Wattforum_2022	0.136	0.363	0.275
Multimar Wattforum_2023	0.165	0.367	0.266
Naturcamping Prinzen_2022	0.171	0.500	0.305
Naturcamping Prinzen_2023	0.362	0.626	0.368
Neuschwanstein_2022	0.107	0.261	0.188
Neuschwanstein_2023	0.114	0.305	0.254
Scharbeutz_2022	0.161	0.425	0.371
Scharbeutz_2023	0.144	0.441	0.388
Wertheim Village_2022	0.093	0.172	0.089
Wertheim Village_2023	0.082	0.104	0.033
Willingen_2022	0.108	0.214	0.058
Willingen_2023	0.103	0.203	0.083

The Corrected Gini value was computed with the DescTools package, the Relative TCSI was computed with the spatialct package.

Table 1 shows three indicators (Top 3 share, Corrected Gini and Relative TCSI) for all PoI and both years. Figure 1 is a visualisation of the same data for the Relative TCSI.

Figure 5: RTCSI values for eleven PoI, two years each

Discussion

Comparing the heterogeneous POIs without considering the annual differences between the two years, the data confirm the visual analysis. POIs such as Naturcamping Prinzenholz, the beach in Scharbeutz and the edutainment centre Multimar Wattforum exhibit higher seasonality values across all metrics, indicating a strong seasonal concentration of visitors. These PoI experience an influx of visitors during specific times of the year, such as holidays or special events. It is remarkable that the outdoor spots such as the beach, the campsite or the zoo all show high seasonalities, but the Willingen ski resort or the Bayerischer Wald nationalpark do not. Higher values could have been expected for both areas. Instead, the nationalpark shows among all spots and among all metrics one of the lowest seasonality. Urban like spots such as the Wertheim Village shopping centre, der Jungfernstieg in the city centre of

Hamburg or the Deutsches Museum on the contrast show lower values, suggesting a more evenly distributed visitor pattern throughout the year.

Upon examining the changes between the years 2022 and 2023 for each POI, it is evident that all of the locations experienced shifts in their seasonal patterns. Most spots show an increase in seasonality from 2022 to 2023. For instance, Naturcamping Prinzenholz shows a significant increase in all metrics from 2022 to 2023, suggesting an intensification of its seasonal visitor concentration, also visible in the high peak in 2023 (Figure 8). Similarly, the Dünentherme in St. Peter-Ording and the zoo Hagenbecks Tierpark also display increases in their indices, indicating growing seasonality. Conversely, the Deutsches Museum, Multimar Wattforum and Wertheim Village exhibit a decrease in their seasonality. However, special circumstances could play a role here. For example, seasonality at the campsite could have been caused by an extraordinary event as seen in the first half of the year in 2022 (Figure 4) The construction work and the re-opening of the Deutsches Museum in 2022 will certainly also play a special role in the data.

When comparing the different seasonality indicators, it can be seen that all three indicators usually show an increasing or decreasing seasonality. They therefore behave in the same way. However, this is not always the case. For example, for the shopping centre and the ski area, the RTCSI indicates rising seasonality while the others fall. The situation is similar for the Edutainment Centre, but the RTCSI shows a falling seasonality here, while the others diagnose a rising seasonality from 2022 to 2023. The beach is the only exception here: while the share of the top 3 falls from 2022 to 2023, the other indicators rise.

Based on our data, we can see that no matter which indicator we look at, the beach, the campsite and the Edutainment Centre show the highest seasonality. All three locations are heavily dependent on the weather. While the first two usually rely on good weather, the Edutainment Centre is a suitable indoor alternative when the weather is bad (at least in this specific case in Schleswig-Holstein). With regard to the low seasonality, there are differences in the indicators, which can be explained by the abilities of the RTCSI (high temporal sensitivity and ability to detect multiple seasonal peaks). It shows the lowest values for the urban POIs of the museum, the shopping centre and the city centre. While for the other two, the shopping centre is also included in the low 3, but here, the National Park comes receives also very low values for both indicators.

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Annex: Example of Indicators

Monthly data

Month	Data1	Data2	Data3	Data4
1	8.33	3.00	12.00	0.00
2	8.33	2.00	15.00	0.00
3	8.33	3.00	12.00	0.00
4	8.33	5.00	2.00	0.00
5	8.33	5.00	2.00	0.00
6	8.33	15.00	13.00	0.00
7	8.33	25.00	16.00	100.00
8	8.33	20.00	13.00	0.00
9	8.33	10.00	2.00	0.00
10	8.33	5.00	2.00	0.00
11	8.33	2.00	1.00	0.00
12	8.33	5.00	10.00	0.00
SUM	100	100	100	100
MEAN	8.33	8.33	8.33	8.33

The values represent fictitious data of monthly tourism demand over the course of a year. All have a sum of 100 and a mean of 8.33.

- Data1 has no seasonality. All months have the same share.
- Data2 is unimodal with a high season in summer.
- Data3 is bimodal with high seasons in summer and winter.
- Data4 is maximum concentrated with only one month having all the demand.

	Data1	Data2	Data3	Data4
SRange	0.00	23.00	15.00	100.00
SyRatio	1.00	3.00	1.92	12.00
Syl	1.00	0.33	0.52	0.08
SlRatio	1.00	12.50	16.00	(0)
WSR	1.00	4.00	0.92	(0)
TOP3	25.00	60.00	44.00	100.00
AAD	0.00	6.11	5.44	15.28
VAR	0.00	53.56	32.56	763.89
SD	0.00	7.32	5.71	27.64
VC SD	0.00	0.88	0.68	3.32
VC VAR	0.00	6.43	3.91	91.67
Gini (original)	0.000	0.445	0.372	0.917
Gini (corrected)	0.000	0.485	0.405	1
Theil TT	0.000	0.336	0.279	n.d.
Theil TL	0.000	0.350	0.399	n.d.
Hoover	0.000	0.367	0.329	0.917
Herfindahl	0.083	0.148	0.122	1.000
RTCSI	0.000	0.440	0.197	1.000

The Gini, Theil TT and Herfindahl values were computed with the *ineq* package for R (Zeileis & Kleiber, 2014), the Theil L values with the *REAT* package (Wieland, 2021). *DescTools* (Signorell et al., 2024) computes the Gini index with bias correction. Hoover values were computed with the *REAT* and *EconGeo* package. RTCS values were computed with *SCalc* (Lo Magno, 2017) and the *spatialct* package for R (Lo Magno et al., 2020).

Weekly data

In a similar way, we constructed four test datasets to represent no seasonality (Data1), unimodal (Data2), bimodal (Data3) and maximum seasonality (Data4), based upon the 52 weeks of the year. In the bimodal case (Data3), high values occur in the weeks 51–52, 1–2 and 24–26.

	Data1	Data2	Data3	Data4
SRange	0.00	9.00	9.00	100.00
SyRatio	1.00	5.20	5.20	52.00
Syl	1.00	0.19	0.19	0.02
SlRatio	1.00	10.00	10.00	(0)
WSR	1.00	0.37	1.08	0.00
TOP3	3.00	12.50	30.00	100.00
AAD	0.00	64.62	83.08	196.15
VAR	0.00	3.99	6.30	188.61
SD	0.00	2.00	2.51	13.73
VC SD	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.14
VC VAR	0.00	2.08	3.28	98.08
Gini (original)	0.000	0.392	0.427	0.981
Gini (corrected)	0.000	0.400	0.435	1.000
Theil TT	0.000	0.348	0.509	n.d.
Theil TL	0.000	0.277	0.384	n.d.
Hoover	0.000	0.323	0.415	0.981
Herfindahl	0.019	0.040	0.052	1.000
RTCSI	0.000	0.393	0.217	1.000

In this example, the Gini, Theil and Hoover coefficients in the bimodal case are even higher than in the unimodal case, while the RTCSI gives a lower seasonality value for the bimodal case.

Further information

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